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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Most of the women in our environment abhor hysterectomy but it remains the only option in most cases in our practice of gynaecology due to late presentation when it becomes more difficult to offer a less radical management options. This study aims to evaluate the indications, clinical characteristics and management outcome in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. This is a retrospective analysis of all Hysterectomies performed from 1st January, 2000 through 31st December, 2005 at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital. There were 170 cases of elective hysterectomy out of a total of 1025 elective major gynaecological surgeries during the study period with hysterectomy prevalence of 16.6%. The mean age of the patients was 46.5 years, 21(13.55%) of the women were nulliparous. The major indications were symptomatic uterine fibroid 55.5%, ovarian tumour 14.8% and uterovaginal prolapsed 8.4%. The surgery in 92 (59.4%) patients was performed by consultants. The crude morbidity and case fatality rates was 45.45% and 3.87% respectively. Elective hysterectomy for gynaecological condition remains a valid management option in our environment. The use of peri-operative antibiotics is advised to reduce the incidence of post-operative morbidity.

Key words: Hysterectomy, Indication, Niger Delta, Outcome.

INTRODUCTION

Hysterectomy which is extirpation of the uterus surgically is commonly performed by gynaecologist for various reasons. It is the commonest major gynaecological operation in the developed countries; about 600,000 hysterectomies are performed annually in the United States, and about a third and a quarter of women will have a hysterectomy during their life time and before menopause respectively. (2003; Okjonofua and Odunsi (eds.), 2009; Patricia et al) Most women undergo the surgery because of the negative impact of urinary incontinence, abnormal uterine bleeding and chronic pelvic pain on their quality of life which in many cases have not been resolved by less radical options. (2003; Patricia et al)

In the developed countries hysterectomy is accepted readily, the case is however, very different in developing countries where there is a strong aversion to hysterectomy for reason of fear for surgery, loss of femininity and sexual rejection by their spouse or because of their strong cultural belief or religious attachment to preservation of menstruation and childbearing.(2003;Okjonofua and Odunsi (eds.),2003; Omigbodun and Ayinde). The commonest indications for hysterectomy in our environment remains uterine fibroid and menstrual disorder as in the developed countries except that the uterine fibroid is generally larger than it's the case in developed countries because they usually present late. (2004; Okogbenin et al) The other indications include; dysfunctional bleeding, endometriosis, and pelvic organ prolapse. (2009; Patricia et al).

Majority of women have relief from their symptoms after Hysterectomy with associated high level of satisfaction with the procedure; however, the procedure is not without it's complications; including the long term risk of having twice the rates of operations for stress incontinence and for prolapse compared with non-hysterectomized women irrespective of the technique or type hysterectomy, furthermore, weight gain is another complain that is frequently seen after hysterectomy. ((2009; Patricia et al, 2008;Altman et al , 1994; Carlson et al)

There is paucity of data on elective hysterectomy for gynaecological condition in our environment and a baseline data based on the local population will be helpful to ascertain the indications, clinical characteristics and the pattern of morbidity associated with elective hysterectomies which are the aims of this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is a 5-year retrospective review of all cases of elective hysterectomy for gynaecological conditions managed at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital a tertiary institution in Rivers state Nigeria from 1st January 2000 through 31st December 2005. The sources of information were patient case notes, gynaecological ward records and theater records. Information regarding the socio-demographic characteristics, presenting symptoms, clinical findings, intraoperative and postoperative complications, associated morbidity and mortality pattern were collected. The information obtained was coded and transferred onto a pro forma designed for the study. Data collected were analyzed using Epi Info version 3.5. Approval for this work was given by the Ethical Committee of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital.

RESULTS

There were 170 cases of elective hysterectomy out of a total of 1025 elective major gynaecological surgery during the period with hysterectomy prevalence of 16.6%, however; only 155(91.2%) case notes were available for analysis.

The age of the woman ranges between 22 to 80 years; the mean age was 46.5 years. 115 (74.2%) of the women were involved in some form of occupation. Majority of the women 138 (86.0%) were married, 231 (20%) of the women were postmenopausal, while 124 (80%) were premenopausal, 21(13.6%) of the women were nulliparous. Table 1.

Amongst those that had abdominal hysterectomy, the commonest mode of presentation was abdominal swelling and menstrual disorder, while amongst the women that had vaginal hysterectomy was something coming down their vaginal and vaginal discharge. This is illustrated in figure 1.

The commonest indication for elective hysterectomy was uterine fibroid with or without menorrhagia, with ovarian pathology coming a distant second. As a result, the preferred route for elective hysterectomy was abdominal in 142 (91.6%) cases as shown in Table 2 and 3 respectively. The surgery in 92 (59.4%) patients was performed by consultants.

Additional surgery performed includes; bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy in 42 (27.1%) and in 9 (5.8%) unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy. 4 (2.6%) women had subtotal abdominal hysterectomy due to gross pelvic adhesions. Peri-operative prophylactic antibiotics was uncommon rather prophylactic antibiotics was given post-operatively.

Histological diagnosis was available in 78 (50.3%) cases and was in agreement with the diagnosis in all cases of uterine fibroid; with the exception of one woman who was noted to have leiomyosarcoma. Discordance in diagnosis was commonest amongst ovarian tumor, where 3 women thought to have benign ovarian tumor were reported to have papillary serous cystadenocarcinoma and the other two had serous cystadenocarcinoma. The mean duration of hospital stay after abdominal hysterectomy was 10.0 ± 4.5 days and for vaginal hysterectomy it was 9.3 ± 4.5 days.

Table 4 showed the morbidity and mortality pattern. The crude morbidity rate was 45.5% (72 cases had morbidity). The three commonest morbidities noted were febrile illness 38 (24.5%) anaemia 25 (16.1%) and wound infection 16 (10.3%). There were 6 deaths during the study period giving a case fatality rate of 3.9%.

Table 1: Socio- demographics of the study subjects.

Parameter	variable	n=155	%
Age (years)	18 to 35	14	9.0
	36 to 40	30	19.4
	31 to 45	36	23.2
	46 to 50	38	24.5
	>50	37	23.9
Parity	0	21	13.5
	1 to 4	86	55.5
	>5	48	31.0
Marital status	single	8	5.2

	married	138	89.0
	divorced	5	3.2
	widow	4	8.6
Education	nil	41	26.5
	primary	59	38.1
	secondary	37	23.9
	tertiary	18	16.5
Occupation	unemployed	18	11.6
	housewife	35	22.6
	petty trader	27	17.4
	farmer	17	11.0
	civil servant	58	37.4
	business	18	11.6

Figure 1: Mode of Presentation

Table 2: Indication for hysterectomy

Pre-operative diagnosis	Number of cases	Percentages (%)
Uterine fibroid + menorrhagia	91	58.71
Ovarian mass	23	14.84
Uterovaginal prolapse	13	8.39
Cervical cancer	5	3.22
Endometrial cancer	5	3.22
Cervical intraepithelial neoplasia	5	3.22
Dysfunctional uterine bleeding	4	2.58
Chronic PID	3	1.94
Menorrhagia only	3	1.94
Septic abortion	2	1.29
Choriocarcinoma	1	0.65
Total	155	100

Table 3:Types of hysterectomy

Hysterectomy	Number of cases	Percentages (%)
Total abdominal hysterectomy	138	89.0
Vaginal hysterectomy	13	8.4
Subtotal abdominal hysterectomy	4	2.6
Total	155	100

Table 4: Post-operative morbidity and mortality

Complications	Number of cases	Percentages (%)
Pyrexia	38	24.52
Anaemia	25	16.13
Wound infection	16	10.32
Death	6	3.87
Ureteric injury	4	2.58
Pelvic abscess	4	2.58
Bladder injury	2	1.29
Intestinal obstruction	2	1.29
Vault haematoma	2	1.29
Bowel injury	1	0.64

DISCUSSION

Hysterectomy continues to be relevant in the practice of gynaecology in our environment in spite of the strong aversion by our women (2003; Okonofua and Odunsi (eds.), 2003; Omigbodun and Ayinde). The study revealed a higher prevalence for hysterectomy for gynaecological condition than was reported in other Nigeria studies (2010; Bukar et al, 2010; Geidam et al, 2008; Abe and Omo-Aghoja)

More than half of the patients were in their fourth decade of life and above, same as noted in other studies. (2004; Okogbenin et al, 2010; Bukar et al, 2010; Geidam et al, 2008; Abe and Omo-Aghoja). This is a reflection of the demographics in our environment.

The commonest indication for hysterectomy in our study is symptomatic Uterine fibroid; this is in consonance with other studies. (2010; Bukar et al, 2008; Abe and Omo-Aghoja, 2001; Roberts and Okunola,1998;Oyawoye)

The commonest type was Abdominal hysterectomy, with Vaginal hysterectomy being performed for all cases of uterovaginal prolapsed, this is similar to findings from other centers (2010; Bukar et al, 2010; Geidam et al 2008;

Abe and Omo-Aghoja, 2001; Roberts and Okunola, 1998), however, the prevalence of 8.4% for vaginal hysterectomy in this study, is lower than 20.7%, 19.6% and 14.7 % reported from previous studies. (2010; Bukar et al, 2008 ;

Abe and Omo-Aghoja, 2004; Aksu et al). The parity of the women that had vaginal hysterectomy was in agreement with a previous study from our center and Ilorin respectively. (1997; Balogun, 2004; Ugboma et al)

There was a high proportion of nulliparous women (16.9%), this is higher than findings from previous studies (2010; Bukar, 2001; Roberts and Okunola), this may be due the older age of patients in our study. The association of fibroid with nulliparity and low parity was further reinforced by the findings from this study, which is in agreement with other Nigerian studies. (2002; Aboyeji and Ijaiya, 2004; Komolafe et al)

Subtotal abdominal hysterectomy was performed in 2.6% of the patients due to gross pelvic adhesion; this is higher than 1.1% from Maiduguri, but lower than 4.4% and 5.8% from previous studies (2010; Bukar et al, 2004; Aksu et al, 2007; Kawuwa et al). The shortcomings of subtotal hysterectomy includes retaining the cervix, a potential site for cancer, which usually is difficult to treat, in addition the increase cost of treating other potential cervical pathologies. (2001; Neerja Bhatta)

The study also revealed a high incidence of iatrogenic ureteric injuries (2.58%) at hysterectomy; all injuries occurred at abdominal surgery as was noted in Ibadan (2003; Shittu et al). These patients had dense adhesion with gross pathology that tended to distort the anatomical relationship of the pelvic organ. Intravenous urogram that would have helped to outline the course of the ureter during surgery, thus reducing the incidence of injury was not commonly done during the period under review may be because of the cost consideration.

The study also revealed higher incidence of postoperative morbidity and a longer hospital stay in the women that had abdominal hysterectomy as opposed to those that had vaginal hysterectomy; this is similar to findings from previous studies. (2010; Bukar et al, 1998; Oyawoye 2007; Kawuwa et al). The two commonest morbidity noted were febrile illness and anaemia, this is consonance with other studies. (2010; Bukar et al, 2010; Geidam et al, 2001; Roberts and Okunola)

There were 6 deaths during the study period giving a case fatality rate of 3.9%, this is higher than 1.6% from a similar study. (2008; Abe and Omo-Aghoja)

The advantage of chemoprophylaxis in hysterectomy has been shown in other studies; this may reduce the infectious morbidity documented in this study. (2010; Bukar et al)

It is concluded that alternative conservative measures such as endometrial ablative techniques or use of medical treatment are not readily available in our environment or when available are very costly. In order to reduce the high morbidity and mortality associated with this procedure, there is need for further training and re-training of gynaecologist in the art of vaginal hysterectomy and other radical forms of hysterectomy in addition to use of peri-operative antibiotics.

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